

BETWEEN HISTORY AND CITIZENS' CONSCIOUSNESS: UNDERSTANDING THE CONTEXT AND CHARACTER OF THE NIGERIAN CONSTITUTION AND THE RULE OF LAW IN A GLOBAL AGE

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Abstract

In a society where there is no law, crime is not a sin. Hegel posited that human consciousness is among the goals of universal history as spirit is the basis of all activities and accomplishments. He further stated that freedom is a fruit of mind and it could only be earned by rational will against the subjective will of human. Nigeria as at today approximately has a population of about 200 million people. A clear majority of this population are youths who are obviously unaware of the state of the laws of the land. Neither are they conscious of the dictates of the constitution of the nation because the Constitution and its history since 1960 have not been treated as historical document worthy of special historical attention. It is, therefore, "unavailable" for the school boys and girls. What are the implications of this for nation-building and constitutional development, and the consciousness of the citizenry of the country? It is the objectives of this paper to attempt a critique of the underdevelopment of the discipline of history as a tool for the teaching of the Nigeria Constitution and Rule of Law as an Integral part of the history curriculum in Nigerian secondary schools. It is, therefore, the objective of this paper which desires to make an important contribution to our understanding of the role of history in demonstrating familiarity with the factors that influenced constitution-making in a plural society like Nigeria. This is with the idea of enabling citizens of Nigeria to construct a system of society wherein everybody can be a person, conscious and rational as a prerequisite for national security, integration, and development. To achieve this objective, historical method of data collection, collation and analysis was used.

Keywords: History, Citizens' Consciousness, Nigerian Constitution, Rule of Law, Nation Building, Global Age

Introduction

“History, for Hegel, is the story of the development of the consciousness of freedom in the world, the development of the human spirit¹ in time through the growth of its own self-consciousness”

The basis of any developed nation resides in the constitution by which the people are governed and nations require their citizens to be patriotic and united towards achieving a prosperous and functional system worthy of admiration in the global system. It is this objective that Hegel posited in its lines as stated above. Logically explained in this paper that the past is the presence as posited in the explanation of Spirit as achiever of history:

*“...The difference lies only in the degree of development of this implicit nature. The life of ever-presence Spirit is a cycle of stages on one hand [for philosophy] the stages co-exist side by side; on the other hand [for History] they appear as past. But the phases which Spirit seems to have left behind it, it also possesses in the depth of its present”.*²

One would note that sciences, art, and civil life are entailed in culture as birthing all manner of human endeavours that include science, technology, government or state, as a reflection of means and actualization of History that served as determinant of human growth, consciousness, prosperity and all-

¹ [Another very troubling term is the notorious “Geist”, which means “Spirit,” but also “mind,” “mentality,” “soul,” and “intellect.”] see Hegel, G.W.F., *Introduction to The Philosophy of History*, USA, Hackett Publishing Company, 1988

² Hegel, G.W.F., *Introduction to The Philosophy of History*, USA, Hackett Publishing Company, 1988

round developments in economic and social institutions³ (It is freedom that makes a nation and creates wealth and riches).

As History is the embodiment of human consciousness, a nation's constitution and rule of law are mechanisms through which nations achieve its course. The term "rule of law" as an ancient concept has virtually become the most popular phraseology in today's democratic governance. Rule of law is a derivate from natural law. Natural Law is also the basis of fundamental human rights and was relied on to advance arguments on democracy. According to St. Thomas Aquinas, natural law is "an ordinance of reason for the common good made by him who has care of the community."⁴ He stated further that natural law "is produced by the unaided reason, is common to man both Christian and pagan."⁵

Briefly put, natural law is a law of reason, rightness and truth. These attributes are subsumed in the concept of the rule of law. Aristotle opined that rule of law is connected with the question "whether it is better to be ruled by the best man or the best laws."⁶ Aristotle's position contrasts with Plato's who said government by laws and governments by wise man are alternatives "when it is clear that even the wisest ruler cannot

³ Daron Acemoglu and James A. Robinson, *Why Nations Fail: The Origin of Power, Prosperity, and Poverty*, Crown Publishers, New York, 2012

⁴ Anton-Hermann Chroust and Frederick A. Collins Jr., *The Basic Ideas in the Philosophy of Law of St. Thomas Aquinas as Found in the "Summa Theological"*, 26 Marq. L. Rev. 11, 1941. <http://scholarship.law.marquette.edu/mltr/vol26/iss1/2>

⁵ Anton-Hermann Chroust and Frederick A. Collins Jr., *The Basic Ideas in the Philosophy of Law of St. Thomas Aquinas as Found in the "Summa Theological"*, 26 Marq. L. Rev. 11, 1941. <http://scholarship.law.marquette.edu/mltr/vol26/iss1/2>

⁶https://www.researchgate.net/publication/251342294_The_Natural_Law_Theory_of_S_t_Thomas_Aquinas (Retrieved: 4th July, 2023)

dispense with law because law has an impersonal quality which no man, however good, can attain.”⁷

As a concept, rule of law is anchored in the word “law” which implies that man should be ruled or society should be governed not by the rule of man or by the rule of might but rather by the rule of law. The rule of law should not only be enshrined in a given code as a fundamental principle of government, but rather should equally evolve from:

*“Those principles, usages and rules of action applicable to the government and security of persons and property which does not rest for their authority upon any express or positive statute or other written declarations but upon statements of principles found in the decisions of the courts”.*⁸

As a relatively recent and developing concept, the rule of law in Nigeria, and other countries emerging from other forms of dictatorship or tyranny is fragile. These countries have different views of the requirements, contents and context of the rule of law. In some countries what obtains is rule by law rather than rule of law.⁹

Issues and the birth of the Nigeria Constitution

Available historical material points to the fact that before the advent of colonialism in 1861 (annexation of Lagos) and the subsequent January 1, 1914 amalgamation; a tremendous degree of tolerance, accommodation, borrowing and interactions among

⁷https://www.researchgate.net/publication/251342294_The_Natural_Law_Theory_of_S_t_Thomas_Aquinas (Retrieved: 4th July, 2023)

⁸ Fayemi, K, *Deepening the Culture of Constitutionalism. Regional Institutions and Constitutional Development in Africa*, Abuja: Centre for Democracy and Development, 2003.

⁹ Dakas, C.J. “The Nigerian Constitution and Social Justice: Which Way Forward?” *University of Jos: Journal of Political Science*, Vol.1 No.1, 1995

the various ethnic groups existed in works of these scholars.¹⁰ As such they usually referred to themselves as people or traders from Hausaland, Yorubaland, Igboland, and Ibibioland etc.¹¹ Uya, Nnoli, Ndoma-Egba and Ndoma-Egba agreed that the picture of intrinsic and inherent incompatibility of ethnic groups in Nigeria was the handiwork of colonial anthropologists.¹² According to these scholars, European anthropologists first used it as a label of identity and later this was appropriated as a tool of divide and rule by the colonialists. This trend continued till 1914. The amalgamation which brought the protectorates of Northern Nigeria and that of Southern Nigeria with the colony of Lagos was only to pool the resources of the relatively richer territories of the south to meet the cost of running the north and thus, reduce the burden on the British tax payers.¹³ The British therefore achieved territorial integration. By this, they incorporated the various ethnicities into an amalgamated Nigeria. Thus, began the process of acrimony, distrust, suspicion, hatred, culture of parochialism in national affairs and a legacy of tension among the component parts of Nigeria.¹⁴

However, the imperial Order-in-Council that established the Arthur Richards Constitution which became effective on

¹⁰ Aderonmu, J.A. "Federalism, National Question and Patterns of Power Sharing in Nigeria": *Kogi Journal of Politics*. Vol. 1. No. 1 Dept. of Political Science, KSU, Anyingba, 2010, pp. 12-24

¹¹ Nnoli, O., *Ethnic Politics in Nigeria* Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishers, 1978, pp. 35

¹² Ndoma-Egba V. and Ndoma-Egba E., "Forced Unity: The Nationality Question" in Okon E. Uya, *Civil Society and the Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria*. Calabar: Cats Publication, 2000

¹³ Nnonyelu, N.A.U., "Ethnicity, national Interest and National Integration in Nigeria" in Ngozi Ojiakor and G.C. Nnachukwu *Nigerian Socio-Political Development Issues and Problems (ed)*, Enugu John Jocab Publishers, 1997, pp. 143-152

¹⁴ Suberu R. T., "Federation in Africa: The Nigerian Experience in Comparative Perspective" in *Ethnopolitics*, 2009, Vol. 8. No 1

January 1, 1947 contained integrative elements. The purpose of the Constitution as stated in the Nigeria Sessional Paper No. 4 of 1945¹⁵ was:

- (1) To promote the unity of the country;
- (2) To provide adequately for the desire for the diverse elements which made up the country; and
- (3) To secure greater participation of Africans in the discussion of their own affairs.

As noted by Adigwe:

*“The constitution sought to promote the unity of the country by establishing regional councils together with a central council in Lagos... (but) the establishment of regional councils tended to weaken the unity (national integration) of the country”.*¹⁶

This explained why subsequent review or evolutions of a new constitution (1951, 1954 and 1960) were advocated for, from purely ethnic stand-point by the Nigerian representatives.¹⁷ For example, those that represented the North in 1951 Macpherson constitution demanded for parity with the South in representation in the central legislature, those that represented the West called for a revision of the Northern Frontier, so as to exclude the people of Offa, Igbomina and Kabba from the North since they are Yoruba speaking tribes; while the East in conjunction with the North requested for Lagos to be removed from Western Region and made a “no- man’s land”.¹⁸ From the foregoing, it is clear that

¹⁵ Okibe, H. B., *Political Evolution and Constitutional Development in Nigeria 1861 – 1999*, Enugu: Marydan Publishers, 2000

¹⁶ Adigwe, S.U, *Nigerian Education*, Longman Nigeria Ltd; Lagos, Nigeria 1999 p.23

¹⁷ Okibe, H. B., *Political Evolution and Constitutional Development in Nigeria 1861 – 1999*, Enugu: Marydan Publishers, 2000

¹⁸ Yusuf, B.U., “The Federation of Nigeria and the Lessons of the Historical Experiences of the People of Nigeria” in Elaigwu, J.O. Logams, P.C and H.S. Galadima

each of them were preponderantly interested in its hegemony over the others. Invariably, discordant views greeted the motion for “self-government in 1956”¹⁹ which was originally conceived to “present a united front of collective responsibility”.²⁰ Again, as a result of the fears of the minority groups in the Niger-Delta, a commission of enquiry (headed by Henry Willink) was set up and instead of creating states as desired by them, it made a detailed list of fundamental human rights in it stead to cushion it.²¹

With independence in 1960, the stark reality was the need to build a strong and united country despite the presence of over 250 ethnic groups and 466 dialects.²² Thus, it became clear that Nigeria would need integrative mechanisms, just like other plural societies in the world. This object of integrative mechanisms became the object of this paper with analysis of using the Nigerian history as a panacea for understanding the Nigeria constitution and adhering to the rule of law from the youngest in the Nigerian societies to the oldest.

(eds) *Federalism and Nation-Building in Nigeria: The Challenges of the 21st Century*. Abuja, 1994

¹⁹ Ogunojemite, N., Ethnicity, National Interest and National Integration in Nigeria Ibadan: University Press Ltd, 1987, pp. 31 – 36

²⁰ Nnonoyelu, N.A.U. “Ethnicity, national Interest and National Integration in Nigeria” in Ngozi Ojiakor and G.C. Nnachukwu *Nigerian Socio-Political Development Issues and Problems (ed)*, Enugu John Jocab Publishers, 1997, pp. 143-152.

²¹ Aderonmu, J.A. “Federalism, National Question and Patterns of Power Sharing in Nigeria”: *Kogi Journal of Politics*. Vol. 1. No. 1 Dept. of Political Science, KSU, Anyingba, 2010, pp. 12-24

²² Ake, C., “The Nigeria State, Antimonies of a periphery formation” in Ake, C. (ed) *Political Economy of Nigeria*, Longman London, 1996

The Supremacy of the Constitution and the Rule of Law in the Global Age

The rule of law means that the law should be promulgated in accordance with the provisions in the constitution.²³ Rule of law involves first and foremost democratic government by constitutionalism. Democratic government presupposes ‘government of the people, by the people and for the people.’²⁴ This is the very essence of sovereignty that the people rule. The people who are expected to obey the laws of the country are given an opportunity to influence the content of these laws through a popularly elected legislature. Thus all power flows from the people, hence government laws are their laws. Thus, the Nigerian Constitution states that “The Federal Republic of Nigeria shall be a state based on the principles of democracy and social justice.”²⁵ It means rule in public interest against personal interest as distinguished from a factional or tyrannous rule in the interest of a single class or individuals and citizens in turn would prioritize the public interest as Mercy Otis posited while addressing people of United State of America:

“There must be a positive passion for the public goods, the public interest honour, power and glory, established in the minds of the people, or there can be no republican government, nor any real liberty. And this public passion must be superior to all private

²³ Ihonvbere, J., “Principles and Mechanisms of Building a Peoples’ Constitution: Pointers for Nigeria”, in Gidado, M.M et.al (ed) *Nigeria Beyond 1999: Stabilising the Polity Through Constitutional Re-engineering*, Enugu: Chenglo Limited, 2004

²⁴ Ibeanu, O. “Conclusions: A Troubled Path to Democratic Consolidation”, in Jega, A & Ibeanu, O. (ed) *Elections and the Future of Democracy in Nigeria*, Abuja: Nigerian Political Science Association, 2007

²⁵ Ihonvbere, J. “Principles and Mechanisms of Building a Peoples’ Constitution: Pointers for Nigeria”, in Gidado, M.M et.al (ed) *Nigeria Beyond 1999: Stabilising the Polity Through Constitutional Re-engineering*, Enugu: Chenglo Limited, 2004

passions. Men must be ready, they must pride themselves, and be happy to sacrifice their private pleasures, passions and dearest connections, when they stand in competition with the rights of society”²⁶

In the international system, any system of government that is anchored on the rule of law and democratic governance, especially the presidential system of government as obtains in Nigeria, must have separation of powers - i.e. the Executive, the Legislature and the Judiciary.²⁷ Such a separation of powers - division of labour if you like, is a condition precedent to the firm entrenchment of the concept of rule of law in any society. Distinguished authors have eloquently and succinctly stated the *raison d’être* for separation of powers.²⁸

Montesquieu has said that:

“Political liberty is to be found only where there is no abuse of power. But constant experience shows that every man invested with power is liable to abuse it, and carry his authority as far as it will go. To prevent this abuse, it is necessary from the nature of things that one power should be a check on another. When the legislative and the executive powers are united in the same person or body there can be no liberty. Again there is no liberty if the judicial power is not separated from the legislative and executive. There would be an end of everything if the same person or body,

²⁶ http://oll.libertyfund.org/reading_room/2022-09-13-a-friend-to-the-revolution-mercy-otis-warren-and-and-the-ordinary-virtues-of-republicanism. Retrieved: 09/10/2023

²⁷ Jinadu, L.A. “Nigerian Federalism and Democracy at Bay: The Responsibility of Political Science”, in Ali, W.O (ed) *Political Reform Conference: Federalism and the National Question in Nigeria*, Lagos: Nigerian Political Science Association, 2005

²⁸ Ntalaja, N.G., *Democracy and Development in Africa: A Tribute to Claude Ake*, AfriGov, Abuja, 2009, p.14

*whether of the nobles or the people, were to exercise all the three powers”.*²⁹

Section 1 of the 1999 constitution makes the constitution supreme and declares its provisions binding on all authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria.

Since Nigeria became independent in 1960 it has had a chequered history of short civilian rules alternating with long military dictatorship. The test of observance of, and adherence to the rule of law first surfaced during the civilian government of President Shehu Shagari. The people of Nigeria were just emerging from the euphoria of independence when to their chagrin and that of the international community, the then government violently and arbitrarily bundled Alhaji Shugaba Abdulrahman out of the country, deported and dumped him at Niger Republic border, ostensibly on the account that he was not a Nigerian, but really because he was a member of the opposition, Great-Nigeria People’s Party in Borno.³⁰ Under military governance, on behalf of the right less people, the constitution is largely suspended.³¹ Thus the military made no pretensions about the adherence to, or observance of the rule of law. Government was by fiat and decree. One of such decrees muzzled the courts and sought to render them impotent and powerless.³²

²⁹ Weiner, M. “Political Integration and Political Development “ in Finkle, J.L.and Gable, R.W., *Political Development and Social Change* (ed). London: Oxford Press, 1965

³⁰ Ramphal, S.S., *Nationalism and Federating nations: Challenges and Prospects*. Lindsore: AP Technology Ltd, 1979, pp. 31-36

³¹ Elaigwu, J.I., “Military Rule and Federalism in Nigeria” in Elaigwu, J.I. and Akindele, R.A. (eds). *Foundations of Nigeria Federalism 1960-1995*, Jos IGSR, 2001

³² Elaigwu, J.I., “Military Rule and Federalism in Nigeria” in Elaigwu, J.I. and Akindele, R.A. (eds). *Foundations of Nigeria Federalism 1960-1995*, Jos IGSR, 2001

The Idea of History and Citizens' Consciousness

At the popular level with which we are concerned here, the concept of Nigerian history should be seen as practical human activity related to the immediate needs of Nigerians and the nation-state as a group to his and their location in time and place and to his and their expectation of the future.³³ Like the knowledge of sciences, the knowledge of history has immense practical significance. Tush for example argued that our sense of what is practicable in the future is formed by an awareness of what has happened in the past.³⁴ As a contact point, history is the source of every knowledge known to man. All the fields of study are products of history.³⁵ The observation of history as the source of other disciplines has been well captured by Roberts, when he posits that:

*"History is the memory of human group experience. If it is forgotten or ignored, we cease in that measure to be human without history we came to be, like victims of collective amnesia groping in the dark for our identity. it is the events recorded in history that have generated all the emotions, the values, the ideals that make life meaningful, that have given men something to live for, struggle over and die for. Historical events have created all the basic human groupings- countries, religions, classes and all the loyalties that are attached to these"*³⁶.

Meanwhile, it has been argued that there continues link between the past and present. It is this agreement that constitutes a fulcrum

³³ Egbefo, O.D., "Nigeria History: A Panacea for National Integration and Sustainable Democracy in Nigeria" A Paper to be Presented at the Faculty Seminar, Faculty of Education and Arts, IBBUL 2010

³⁴ Tosh, J. *The Essence of History* London Macmillan 1977, pp. 63-65

³⁵ Ajayi, J. F. & Alagoa, E.J. (1980) "Nigeria Before 1800: Aspects of Economic Development and Inter-Group Relations" in Obaro Ikime, *Groundwork of Nigeria History* (ed), Abeokuta, Abuja, Heinemann Educational BKS publishers, pp. 1 -7

³⁶ Robert, V.D., *The Arts of Writing History* London University Press, 1986, p.36

which constitutes a reference point for the activities of man. Describing it, Collingwood in one of his submission stated that: *“...Those societies which retain in changing circumstances a lively sense of their own identity and continuity. . . are to be counted fortunate not because they possess what others lack; but because they have mobilized what none is without and all in fact rely in part on that is History”*³⁷.

Thus, history conceived as a practical human activity is a good tonic for including a sobering awareness of the responsibilities we bear as individuals and groups for everything we think, say or do. In other words it should teach us that it men that make the history they live through and after them. It is because men make history that they bear the consequences of history. This is only natural justice. History conceived as practical human activity will inculcates social values such as individual initiative, hard work, honesty commitments, loyalty,³ unity, good governance for sustainable democracy and so on because it is the events recorded in a history of a nation that have generated all the emotion, that have given citizens something to live for, struggle over or die for. In that way history creates a sense of nationalism, genuine efforts at sustainable developments of a country through university education and its products.⁴

Post-colonial Nigeria like all other nations of the world could gain from the knowledge of history. Nations require their citizens to be patriotic and united towards achieving a functional educational system which can better encourage all round development especially in the shaping of communities' priorities and the empowerment of the people which must be built, it cannot be imported. It has to be, domesticated. In other worlds, we have a collective responsibility to mold our own educational system that could empower us. Rowse restated it that:

³⁷ Collingwood, R.G., *The Idea of History* London, O.U.P., 1956, p12

“One of the greatest advantages of history is that the subject grows with you from a very elementary stage to the cast refinement of ripe maturity and skeptical wisdom. Through history children come to know about their nations past and present. A sense of belongingness and complete loyalty to a larger abstraction called nation then germinates and natures”³⁸.

In other words, in history, Nigerians salvation or doom should be shown as likely to come from what Nigerians think, say and do, not from some extra-terrestrial force.³⁹ For instance if Shehu Uthman Dan Fodio made possible the Islamic Revolution which overtook and changed Hausa society from 1804, a determined and properly motivated Nigerian society and state could set us on the path of our desire goal by advancing a “Nigerian Constitution”⁴⁰ that would guarantee obedience to the rule of law. That results in the transformation of the whole societal system and enhancement of the individuals capacity to realize his inherent potentials and to cope effectively with the challenges of life.⁴¹ Such processes ultimately lead to the achievement of whatever is regarded as a general good for the

³⁸ A. L. Rowse, *The uses of History*, Oxford: Hodder and Stoughton 1946, p.166

³⁹ Thomas, A.W., “The Meaning of Nationhood” In Allien, T., *Integration and Development in Nigeria*, Oxford University Press in Collaboration with the Nigeria Open University 2001. p.28

⁴⁰ Constitution borne out of the needs of the Nigeria societies as USA did consistently after the American revolution 1775-1783 (After several failed attempts at creating a government, a 1787 convention is called to draft a new legal system for the United States. This new Constitution provides for increased federal authority while still protecting the basic rights of its citizens). They were persistent by ratifying and debating on the incorporation of bills until it became a sacred object of their national pride in the global age.

⁴¹ Osaro, G.E., *The Meaning of Nigerian History*, Ibadan University Press, Ibadan University Press, Ibadan, 1989 p.25

society at large. This imperative came more forcefully to the fore at the dawn of the 21st century with several countries coming up with various development agenda for the new millennium and adoption of the United Nations, Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) agenda.⁴² The drive for sustainable development also came against the background of the quest for effective university system as a central concern in international effort for sustainable development for global acceptance. In other words, whatever, the aspiration of any polity/entity, such can only be achieved within an atmosphere of peaceful coexistence of citizens or groups and a harmonious relation between the rulers and the ruled.⁴³ As Claude Ake notes, the task of societal or national development is one that has the people as the central focus and object of development.⁴⁴ Thus nothing could be farther from the truth. For one thing this view arises primarily from the mistaken view that history means the record and activity of a state, rather than the record and activity of a people or peoples. We should see our history not as the history of a state, but as history of peoples. With this again, Nigerian history would come to mean not the record and activities of a Nigeria state, but the record and activities of the peoples who from as far back as Stone Age times had elected the Nigerian area as their home.⁴⁵

⁴² Egbefo, O.D., "Nigeria History: A Panacea for National Integration and Sustainable Democracy in Nigeria" A Paper to be Presented at the Faculty Seminar, Faculty of Education and Arts, IBBUL 2010

⁴³ Egbefo, O.D., "Nigeria History: A Panacea for National Integration and Sustainable Democracy in Nigeria" A Paper to be Presented at the Faculty Seminar, Faculty of Education and Arts, IBBUL 2010

⁴⁴ Ake, C., "The Nigeria State, Antimonies of a periphery formation" in Ake, C. (ed) *Political Economy of Nigeria*, Longman London, 1996

⁴⁵ Ake, C., "The Nigeria State, Antimonies of a periphery formation" in Ake, C. (ed) *Political Economy of Nigeria*, Longman London, 1996

Ending the Analysis of this Paper

The advances in sciences, technology, politics, economics and social institutions of the global age are reflections of the consciousness of the human spirit which could only be assured with the elevation of history; teaching the reflective memories to understanding the requirements of the constitution in obedience to the rule of law. Every human has the ability for a self-determination with history teaching emancipation and enlightenment, aiming at enabling people to construct a system of society wherein everyone could be regarded as free persons and autonomous, “simply by virtue of being a human; conscious and rational”. The international system has required nations to create an identity for advancing the course of human developments by obeying natural laws and principles; which would only be guided by continuous ratification of the nation’s constitution looking at history for citizens’ consciousness.

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